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YUQORI TARTIBLI HOSILA QATNASHGAN ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN TESKARI MASALA

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Maqolaning boshlang'ich shartida yuqori tartibli hosila qatnashgan issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun teskari masala yechimini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Avvalo, issiqlik tenglamasi uchun to'g'ri masala yechimini aniq shaklda keltiriladi, bunda masala yechilishi uchun yetarli shartlarni ko'rsatiladi.

Teskari masala yechimining o'ziga xosligi boshlang'ich chegaraviy masala yechimi asosida boshlang'ich shartlarni aniqlash uchun ko'rib chiqiladi. Bunda tenglamaning uzluksiz funksiyalar sinfidagi yagona yechimini topishga asoslanib, teskari masalaning yagona yechilishi uchun teoremlar olinadi.

Teskari yechim tenglama o'ng tomoni yechimini topish masalasiga mos keladigan xos funksiyalar tizimiga muvofiq Furrye qatori shaklida tuziladi.

$\Omega = \{(x, t) : 0 \leq x \leq l, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ to'g'ri to'rtburchak sohada

$$u_t(x, t) - u_{xx}(x, t) = f(x) \cdot g(x), \quad g(x) \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi uchun quyidagi, chegaraviy

$$u(0, t) = u(l, t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich

$$u(x, t) = \psi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l \quad (3)$$

va

$$\frac{\partial^k u}{\partial t^k}(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l, \quad 1 \leq k \in N \quad (4)$$

qo‘shimcha shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, t)$ yechim va $f(x)$ funksiyani topish masalasini qaraymiz.

Masala yechimining yagonaligi.

1-teorema. Agar (1)-(3) masalaning yechimi mavjud bo‘lsa, u holda bu yechim yagona bo‘ladi.

Isbot. $0 \leq x \leq l$ kesmada $\varphi(x) = 0$ va $g(x) = 1$ bo‘lsin. $\bar{\Omega}$ to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchakda $u(x, t) = 0$ va $f(x) = 0$ tengliklar o‘rinli ekanligini ko‘rsatamiz.

Quyidagi

$$U_n(t) = \int_0^l u(x, t) X_n(x) dx, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (5)$$

integralni qaraymiz.

Bu yerda

$$X_n(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sin \lambda_n x, \quad \lambda_n = \frac{n\pi}{l}, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots \quad (6)$$

$L_2(0, l)$ da to‘la ortonormalangan sistema bo‘ladi .

(5) tenglikni t ga nisbatan differensiallab, bir jinsli $u_t - u_{xx} = 0$ tenglamadan foydalanib

$$U_n'(t) = \int_0^l u_t(x, t) X_n(x) dx \quad (7)$$

va

$$U_n''(t) = \int_0^l u_{xx}(x, t) X_n(x) dx \quad (7^*)$$

tengliklarga ega bo‘lamiz.

(7) integralni bo‘laklab integrallab,

$$U_n'(t) + \lambda_n^2 \cdot U_n(t) = f_n \quad (8)$$

birinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamaga ega bo‘lamiz.

Bu tenglamaning umumiy yechimi

$$U_n(t) = C_n(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}$$

$$U_n'(t) = C_n'(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} - \lambda_n^2 C_n(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} \quad (9) \text{ ga teng.}$$

$$C_n'(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} - \lambda_n^2 C_n'(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + \lambda_n^2 C_n(t)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} = f_n$$

$$C_n'(t) = f_n e^{\lambda_n^2 t}$$

$$\int_0^l C_n'(\tau) d(\tau) = f_n \int_0^l e^{\lambda_n^2 \tau} d\tau$$

$$C_n(t) = C_n(0) + f_n \int_0^l e^{\lambda_n^2 \tau} d\tau = C_n(0) + \frac{f_n}{\lambda_n^2} (e^{\lambda_n^2 t} - 1) \quad (10)$$

$$U_n(t) = \left[C_n(0) + \frac{f_n}{\lambda_n^2} (e^{\lambda_n^2 t} - 1) \right] e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} = C_n(0)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + \frac{f_n}{\lambda_n^2} (1 - e^{-\lambda_n^2 t})$$

(9) tenglikka $U_n(0) = 0$ shartidan foydalanib $C_n(t)$ ni topib oldik.

Umumiy yechimni t o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha k marta differensiallab,

$$U_n^{(k)}(t) = (-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot C_n(0)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + \frac{f_n}{\lambda_n^2} \cdot (-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}$$

$$U_n^{(k)}(t) = (-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot C_n(0)e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + f_n \cdot (-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1} \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} \quad (9^*)$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. $U_n^{(k)}(0) = \varphi_n, \Rightarrow U_n^{(k)}(t) = (-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot C_n(0) + f_n \cdot (-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1} = \varphi_n \Rightarrow$

$$C_n(0) = \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k} - \frac{f_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)}$$

$$U_n(t) = \frac{\varphi_n \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k} - \frac{f_n \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}}{(-\lambda_n^2)} + \frac{f_n \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}}{(-\lambda_n^2)} + \frac{f_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)}$$

$$U_n(t) = \frac{\varphi_n \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k} + \frac{f_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)}$$

Demak (9) yechim $U_n^{(k)} = 0$ shartni qo'llab f_n hadini topib olamiz. Ya'ni (9) yechim $U_n(t) = 0$ $L_2(0, l)$ da $X_n(x)$ ortonormalangan sistema bo'lgani va $X_n(x)$ funksiyaning to'laligidan $\bar{\Omega}$ sohaning hamma joyida $u(x, t) \equiv 0$ va $f(x) = 0$ bo'ladi.

Masala yechimining mavjudligi.

Yuqoridagi (1)-(3) masalaning $u(x, t)$ yechimini Furiye

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot u_n(t) \quad (10)$$

qatori ko'rinishda qidiramiz. (10) Furiye qatorini (1) issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasining $u_t - u_{xx} = 0$ bir jinsli tenglamasiga qo'llasak, quyidagi Dirixle masalasiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$X_n''(x) + \lambda_n^2 X_n(x) = 0.$$

Bu Dirixle masalaning yechimi $X_n(x) = C_1 \cos \lambda_n x + C_2 \sin \lambda_n x$ ga teng bo'ladi.

Endi $f(x)$ funksiyani Furiye qatoriga yoyamiz.

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot f_n, \quad (11)$$

bu yerda

$$f_n = \int_0^l X_n(x) \cdot f(x) dx.$$

(10) va (11) tengliklarni (1) tenglamaga qo'llab quyidagi

$$u_n'(t) + \lambda_n^2 u_n(t) = f_n \quad (12)$$

birinchi tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamani olamiz. (12) tenglamaning (4) boshlang'ich shartini qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi

$$u_n(t) = \varphi_n \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + \frac{f_n}{\lambda_n^2} (1 - e^{-\lambda_n^2 t}) \quad \text{bo'ladi.} \quad (13)$$

Bu yerda φ_n , $\psi(x)$ funksiyaning Furiye koeffitsiyenti:

$$\psi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \varphi_n, \quad (14)$$

$$\psi_n = \int_0^p X_n(x) \cdot \varphi(x) dx. \quad (15)$$

(13) yechimdagi f_n noma'lum koefitsiyentni, (3) qo'shimcha shartdan (ya'ni $u_n^{(k)}(0) = \varphi(x)$) foydalanib topamiz va u quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$f_n = \lambda_n^2 \cdot \psi_n - \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1} \cdot e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} \quad (16)$$

Bu yerda ψ_n , $\psi(x)$ funksiyaning Furiye koefitsiyenti:

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \psi(x) \quad (17)$$

$$\psi_n = \int_0^l X_n(x) \cdot \psi(x) dx. \quad (18)$$

(16) koefitsiyentni (13) yechimga qo'yib, (13) yechimni (10) Furiye qatoriga qo'yib, (1) tenglamaning (2), (3) va (4) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi

$$U_n(t) = \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot e^{\lambda_n^2 t}} + \psi_n - \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} = \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k} \left(\frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 t}} - \frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} \right) + \psi_n$$

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \left[\frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^k} \left(\frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 t}} - \frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} \right) + \psi_n \right] \quad (19)$$

yechimiga ega bo'lamiz.

(16) koefitsiyentni (11) qatorga qo'llab biz qidirayotgan

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \left(\lambda_n^2 \cdot \psi_n - \frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1} e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} \right), \quad (20)$$

funksiyaga ega bo'lamiz.

Endi (19) yechimning quyidagi ba'zi zarur bo'lgan hosilalarini hisoblaymiz:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \left[\frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1}} \cdot \frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 t}} \right] \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \left(\frac{\varphi_n}{(-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1}} \left(\frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 t}} - \frac{1}{e^{\lambda_n^2 T}} \right) - \lambda_n^2 \cdot \psi_n \right), \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial^k u}{\partial t^k} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} X_n(x) \cdot \left\{ (-\lambda_n^2)^k \cdot C_n(0) e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} + f_n \cdot (-\lambda_n^2)^{k-1} \cdot e^{-\lambda_n^2 t} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Endi masalaning yechimi va uning hosilalarini baholaymiz. Qatorlarning taqqoslash alomatiga asosan, quyidagi qatorlarni baholash yetarlidir.

1-Lemma. Agar $\psi(x) \in C_2^3(0, l)$, $\psi(x) \in L_2(0, l)$, $\varphi(0) = \varphi(l) = 0$, $x \in [0, l]$ tenglik o‘rinli bo‘lsa, u holda (7)

qator $\overline{\Omega}$ sohada absolyut va tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo‘ladi.

Isbot. $X_n(x) \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}}$ tengsizlikdan foydalanib, (24) qatorni quyidagicha yozib olamiz.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |X_n(x) \cdot (-\lambda_n^2) \cdot \psi_n| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2 \cdot |\psi_n|. \quad (25)$$

Bu tengsizlikning o‘ng tomonini baholashda ψ_n Furye koeffitsiyentini uch marta bo‘laklab integrallab quyidagi tenglikni olamiz:

$$|\psi_n| = \frac{1}{\lambda_n^3} |\psi_n^{(3)}|. \quad (26)$$

(26) tenglikni (25) ga qo‘llab

$$\sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2 \cdot |\psi_n| = \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \cdot |\psi_n^{(3)}|$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Koshi-Bunyakovskiy tengsizligi va Parseval tengligiga asosan quyidagi

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |X_n(x) \cdot (-\lambda_n^2) \cdot \psi_n| \leq \sqrt{\frac{l}{3}} \left\| \frac{\partial^3 \psi(x)}{\partial x^3} \right\|_{L_2(0, l)}$$

tasdiq o‘rinli bo‘ladi [16].

2-Lemma. Agar $\varphi(x) \in C^1(0, l)$, $\varphi(x) \in L_2(0, l)$ da

$$\frac{\partial^{2l} \psi(0)}{\partial x^{2l}} = \frac{\partial^{2l} \psi(l)}{\partial x^{2l}} = 0, \quad l = \overline{0, 1} \quad \text{tenglik o‘rinli bo‘lsa, u holda (7*)}$$

qator $\overline{\Omega}$ sohada absolyut va tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo‘ladi.

Isbot. (7*) qatorni baholashda g_n Furye koeffitsiyentini bir marta bo'laklab integrallab, Koshi-Bunyakovskiy tengsizligidan foydalanib quyidagi bahoga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |X_n(x) \cdot g_n| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\psi_n| = \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \cdot \psi_n' \right| \leq \sqrt{\frac{l}{3}} \left\| \frac{\partial \psi(x)}{\partial x} \right\|_{L_2(0,l)},$$

bu yerda

$$\psi_n' = \int_0^l \frac{\partial \psi(x)}{\partial x} \sqrt{\frac{2}{l}} \cos \lambda_n x dx.$$

2-teorema. Agar $\varphi(x) \in C^3(0,l)$, $\psi(x) \in L_2(0,l)$ bo'lib, quyidagi

$$\varphi(0) = \varphi(l) = 0, \quad \varphi''(0) = \varphi''(l) = 0, \quad \psi(0) = \psi(l) = 0$$

chegaraviy shartlar bajarisa, (19)-(23) qatorlar Ω sohada absolyut va tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. (1)-(4) masalaning (1) tenglamani, (2)-(4) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi $u(x,t)$ va $f(x)$ funksiyalar mavjud bo'ladi.

Isbot. Yuqoridagi lemmalar isbotidan ma'lumki (19)-(23) qatorlar Ω sohada absolyut va tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. (19) va (20) yechimlar (1) tenglamani va (2)-(4) shartlarni qanoatlantiradi. (2) chegaraviy shart esa $X_n(x)$ xos funksiya hisobidan bajariladi.

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